

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION ON THE E- SERVICE QUALITY AND FOOD QUALITY OF SELECTED ONLINE DELIVERIES

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ABSTRACT

This research study focuses on the satisfaction of consumers regarding the quality of e-services and food provided by two distinct online delivery applications, namely food delivery service and .Assessing millennial satisfaction in regards to the Dwi Suhartanto-introduced online food delivery service framework in 2019 is critical to figuring out the features and customer satisfaction levels pertaining to the quality of the food and e-services offered by the selected online delivery platforms.. Employing a comparative quantitative approach, this research utilized a questionnaire-based survey and purposive sampling to gather information from a total of 120 participants utilizing the aforementioned food delivery services. The examination underscored the significance of either meeting or surpassing the expectations of customers in terms of e-service quality. The outcomes of the Mann-Whitney U Test indicated an absence of noteworthy distinctions between e-service quality and food quality across the designated online delivery applications. The frequent response in the analysis was "agreed" concerning customer satisfaction with e-service quality, particularly in the aspects of fulfillment, efficiency, privacy, and system functionality, alongside the quality of food available through online food delivery services. The study advocates for the continuation of exemplary performance by both delivery applications while also pinpointing specific attributes that necessitate enhancement. The discoveries underscore the critical nature of either meeting or surpassing customer expectations concerning the quality of the e - service and food.

Keywords: *Online Food Delivery, Satisfaction, E-Service Quality, Food Quality*

INTRODUCTION

The Electronic Services or E-Services that may be called nowadays are very rampant in today's generation. It refers to services that are often used for online transactions where it offers communication and information technologies. Our lives are easier now that we use the e-service. These services are becoming more and more significant as a result of their expanding uses in the business, education, and health domains. They are advantageous to all stakeholders, including service providers, consumers, and society at large (AlBalushi, 2021). But in today's generation, E-Service has become convenient to everyone as you just need to download the application, register, browse the specific store outlet, click the order button, and once done, the food will be delivered to you. That turned it into the new standard of living. The primary subjects of this study are the quality of e-services and additional components that promote consumer involvement behaviors on community e-commerce platforms. It demonstrates that encouraging customer involvement behavior is significantly aided by the quality of e-services (interactive service, intelligent fulfillment, system design, and security assurance) (Fan et al., 2022). Wu et al. (2018) define trust as a conviction, assurance, attitude, or anticipation regarding the intention or likely behavior of the customer. For this reason, the market for online meal delivery services is currently very large and very promising. Having and cultivating devoted consumers is crucial in this fiercely competitive business world (Leo et al., 2022).

It has long been known that the quality of services influences customer perception (Luo et al. 2020). Numerous studies have examined how perceived quality affects the interactions between business and customer behavior in the context of consumer perceptions of e-service quality (Hung et al. 2014). Elsharnouby and Mahrous (2015), for instance, contend that an e-service quality affects how users view websites and how likely they are to connect with them. Through virtual communities, it encourages contact and interaction among users of e-commerce platforms, which in turn sparks business transactions (Goraya et al. 2021). As technology exhibits development, the delivery system has also improved to make it easier for customers to order food as well as drinks. This will support satiating your adventurous palate, especially if you enjoy trying out new foods. Thus, in order to obtain a competitive advantage in the food and beverage (F&B) market, service quality is crucial (Kim et al. 2009; Cheng et al. 2012; Cheng et al. 2019a). Allowing customers to deliver food is the aim of the online food delivery (OFD) sector (Banerjee et al. 2019, Chandrasekhar et al. 2019, Annaraud and Berezina, 2020). With the industry's rapid growth in recent years, many customers have also been interested in its service quality. Operators have historically overlooked OFD service quality quite frequently, which has lowered consumer intent and customer happiness (Chen, 2016). Community e-commerce has brought about a number of modifications in traditional e-commerce. However, a community e-commerce platform provides a range of personalized community features, which is a crucial client acquisition strategy. In addition to bringing community e-commerce closer to the general public, customers may be more inclined to participate in highly engaged social activities (Wang et al. 2021). While community e-commerce leverages market segmentation based on virtual communities, traditional e-commerce primarily focuses on high volumes of traffic to maintain competitiveness for business development. According to Chen et al. (2015), community

marketing can assist in accurately positioning clients, resulting in higher customer conversion rates.

Most of these research studies focus on the comparison of how e-service works and its importance, and analysis of the app features. There are a few studies regarding assessing customer satisfaction in online deliveries such as the Food Delivery Service A and Food Delivery Service B. On the other hand, this study will evaluate the experiences of online users or consumers with regard to the quality of the food and e-service. It is crucial that this study be carried out in order to fill up these research gaps.

This study uses the Millennial Satisfaction toward online delivery service model and its corresponding components to assess the satisfaction levels of individuals utilizing online delivery platforms, aiming to address the identified research gap.

Research Questions

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of customer satisfaction on the E- service Quality on online deliveries considering the following factors?
 - 1.1 Efficiency
 - 1.2 Fulfillment
 - 1.3 Privacy
 - 1.4 System
2. What is the assessment of the respondents on the level of satisfaction in food quality of online food delivery considering the following terms?
3. Is there any significant difference between the E-Service Quality and Food Quality of selected online food delivery?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a comparative quantitative research design. Due to its design, quantitative observation enabled the objective collection of data that was primarily focused on numbers and values, whose outcomes could be examined using numerical and statistical approaches (Siedlecki, 2020; Chaudhari, 2021). Additionally, it allowed the researchers to gather data based on their observations of the behavior and characteristics of the respondents in their natural context. Purposive sampling, sometimes referred to as judgment, selective, or subjective sampling, was employed by the researchers in this investigation because it relies on their judgment when choosing which participants to include. This strategy is used by researchers to identify the population and how much data to collect, where the discovery of meaning can benefit from a logical approach. Nikolopoulou (2022) states that "purposive sampling" is a set of non-probability sampling techniques that includes selecting units for your sample depending on their possession of particular attributes. Put differently, purposive sampling involves the "on purpose"

selection of units. When choosing and picking the people, circumstances, or events that can provide the most information to meet the study's objectives, this sampling strategy—often referred to as judgmental sampling—strongly emphasizes the researcher's judgment.

The study's respondents were composed of Food Delivery Service A and Food Delivery Service B users with a total of 120. The primary instrument of this study was an adopted question from different studies of Dwi Suhartanto entitled Millennial Experience with Online Food Home Delivery: A Lesson from Indonesia. (Suhartanto et al., 2019) Another study from the University of Perpetual Help System Laguna entitled Customer Service and Customer Satisfaction in Jollibee (Lopez De Leon et al., 2017) and lastly the study by Rozekhi N. entitled The Influence of Food Quality on Customer Satisfaction in Fine Dining Restaurant: Case in Penang.(Rozekhi et al.,2016) The questionnaires that come from different studies help the researchers to form a research question that helps us to gather our data for this study and serves as the primary instrument for this study. To assess the participants' qualifications, Part I will concentrate on the demographic profile of the respondents. The assessment of customer happiness with the e-service quality of a subset of online deliveries is covered in Part II, and the assessment of customer satisfaction with the food quality of online food delivery is covered in Part III, which focuses on assessing the degree of consumer satisfaction with online deliveries.

The statistical techniques utilized for data interpretation are the weighted mean and the Mann - Whitney U Test. The weighted mean is used as the average of the item values and is calculated by dividing the sum by the total number of items, influenced by each item's value, and used to describe quantitative data. The Mann – Whitney U Test permits the comparison of two conditions, treatments, or groups without requiring the values to follow a normal distribution.

$$\text{Formula: } \underline{WM = \frac{\sum (W_1f_1 + W_2f_2 \dots + w_n f_n)}{N}}$$

Fig.1. Weighted Mean

Where:

WM = weighted mean

f1 = frequency of first cell

w1 = weight of first cell

f2 = frequency of second cell

w2 = weight of second cell

n = number of cases

The t-value is denoted by t in this equation, the means of the two groups under comparison are $\bar{x}_1$ and $\bar{x}_2$, the joint standard error of the two groups is s2, and the total number of observations in each group is n1 and n2.

The difference in group averages over the pooled standard error indicates a more significant difference between the groups, as indicated by a larger t-value.

To determine whether the computed t-value is greater than what would be expected by chance, it can be compared to the data in a critical value chart.

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{s^2 \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right)}}$$

Fig.2.T- Test Formula

A five-point Likert scale has been used by the researchers to measure the assessment of food quality and e-service on online deliveries. It is interpreted by using the five (5) Likert Scale. The questions in the second and third parts of the survey questionnaire will be answered using this 5-point Likert Scale ranging from 1- Strongly Disagree, 2- Disagree, 3- Neutral, 4- Agree, and lastly 5- Strongly Agree.

In Table 2.1, the scale is shown together with a linguistic description as; Strongly Agree (VS) with a mean range of 4.20 to 5.00, Agree (S) with a mean range of 3.40 to 4.19, Neutral (NS) with a mean range of 2.60 to 3.39, Disagree (D) with a mean range of 1.80 to 2.59, and Strongly Disagree (VD) with a mean range of 1.00 to 1.79. The columns' dimensions are as follows:

Table 2.1. Likert Scale Interpretation for Customer Satisfaction

Range of Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Corresponding Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5.00-4.20	Strongly Agree	Very Satisfied	VS
4.19-3.40	Agree	Satisfied	S
3.39-2.60	Neutral	Neither Satisfied	NS
2.59-1.80	Disagree	Dissatisfied	D
1.79-1.00	Strongly Disagree	Very Dissatisfied	VD

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section outlines the examination and presentation of data critical for analyzing the extent of customer satisfaction with the e-service quality of selected online delivery platforms and the quality of food provided by online food delivery services, as well as assessing any significant gaps therein.

Research Question 1: Assessment of the Level of Customer Satisfaction on the E-service Quality on Online Deliveries

**Table 3.1
Level of Customer Satisfaction with the E-Service Quality of Selected Online Deliveries in terms of Efficiency**

Efficiency I felt the online delivery service...	DELIVERY APP A			DELIVERY APP B		
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Was easy to find what I need	3.98	Agree	1	4.28	Strongly Agree	2

Was informative	3.85	Agree	4	4.24	Strongly Agree	4
Can be completed quickly	3.87	Agree	3	4.25	Strongly Agree	3
Was simple to use	3.95	Agree	2	4.40	Strongly Agree	1
Was well organized	3.79	Agree	5	4.19	Agree	5
General Weighted Mean	3.88	Agree		4.27	Strongly Agree	

Table 3.1 presents the level of customer satisfaction with the e-service quality of selected online deliveries in terms of efficiency. The indicator that ranked first was the one that says, “I felt the online delivery service was easy to find what I need” (mean = 3.98) for food delivery service A and “I felt the online delivery service was simple to use.” (mean = 4.40) for food delivery service B. It followed with the one that states, “I felt the online delivery service was simple to use” (mean = 3.95) for food delivery service A and “I felt the online delivery service was easy to find what I need” (mean = 4.28) food delivery service B. Next to it were the indicators that stated, “I felt the online delivery service can be completed quickly.” with a mean of 3.87 for food delivery service A and 4.25 for food delivery service B. Next to it was the indicator that states, “I felt the online delivery service was informative” for both delivery apps with a mean of 3.85 for food delivery service A and 4.24 for food delivery service B. Lastly, the lowest indicator which states “I felt the online delivery service was well organized” is the lowest mean for both delivery app with the mean of 3.79 for food delivery service A and 4.19 for food delivery service B. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents.

In general, the respondents agreed with the respondents about the level of customer satisfaction with the e-service quality of selected online deliveries in terms of efficiency with a general weighted mean of 3.88 for delivery app A. The respondents strongly agreed with the respondents about the level of customer satisfaction with the e-service quality of selected online deliveries in terms of efficiency with a general weighted mean of 4.25 for delivery app B.

According to the findings of Gejendar Sharma and Wang Lijuan (2015) in their study titled "The Effect of Online Service Quality of E-commerce Websites on Use Satisfaction," it was determined that the quality of information and online services played

crucial roles in shaping user satisfaction and ensuring the sustainability of e-commerce technology.

Nevertheless, a significant proportion of online consumers have indicated a need for improvement in selected online delivery services, particularly concerning the organization of data. This is noteworthy as e-commerce is increasingly recognized as a valuable avenue for both individuals and companies to expand their customer base. Consequently, an efficiently organized delivery system, characterized by a network of organizations offering coordinated services, is imperative. Such organized delivery systems lie at the core of endeavors within the hospitality industry aimed at fulfilling consumer expectations reliably.

Table 3.2
Level of Customer Satisfaction with the E-Service Quality of Selected Online Deliveries in terms of Fulfillment

Fulfillment I felt online delivery service...	DELIVERY APP A			DELIVERY APP B		
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Delivered orders when promised	3.77	Agree	5	4.15	Agree	4
Its delivery time was suitable with my time frame	3.76	Agree	6	4.22	Agree	2
Quickly delivered my order	3.87	Agree	4	4.09	Agree	7
Sent the right food items	4.00	Agree	1	4.31	Strongly Agree	1
Keep the product in stock	3.94	Agree	2	4.10	Agree	6
Had honest offerings	3.74	Agree	7	4.18	Agree	3

Accurately deliver the promise	3.92	Agree	3	4.13	Agree	5
General Weighted Mean	3.86	Agree		4.17	Agree	

Table 3.2 presents the level of customer satisfaction with the e-service quality of selected online deliveries in terms of fulfillment. It can be noticed that the indicator that ranked first was the indicator that states, "I felt the online delivery service sent the right food items." with a mean of 4.00 for food delivery service A and 4.31 for food delivery service B. It was followed by the indicator that states, "I felt the online delivery service keep the product in stock" with a mean of 3.94 for food delivery service A and "I felt the online delivery service its delivery time was suitable with my time frame" with a mean of 4.22 for food delivery service B. Next to it were the indicators that stated, "I felt the online delivery service accurately delivered as promised" with a mean of 3.92 for food delivery service A, and "I felt the online delivery service had honest offerings" with a mean of 4.18 for food delivery service B. It was followed by the indicators that state, "I felt the online delivery service quickly delivered my order" with a mean of 3.87 for food delivery service A, and "I felt the online delivery service delivered orders as promised" with a mean of 4.15 for food delivery service B. Next was the indicator that states, "I felt the online delivery service delivered orders as promised" with a mean of 3.77 for food delivery service A and "I felt the online delivery service accurately delivered as promised" with a mean of 4.13 for food delivery service B. It was followed by the indicators that state, "I felt the online delivery service its delivery time was suitable with my time frame" with the mean of 3.3.76 for food delivery service A and "I felt the online delivery service keep the product in stock" with a mean of 4.19 for food delivery service B. Lastly, was the indicator that states, "I felt the online delivery service had honest offerings" with a mean of 3.74 for food delivery service A and "I felt the online delivery service quickly delivered my order" with the mean of 4.10 for food delivery service B which is the lowest indicator. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents.

In general, the respondents agreed with the respondents about the level of customer satisfaction with the e-service quality of selected online deliveries in terms of fulfillment with a general weighted mean of 3.86 for food delivery service A and a general weighted mean of 4.17 for food delivery service B.

In accordance with the findings presented by Zou, Tang, Yilmaz, and Kong (2022) in their study titled "Online Food Delivery Strategies Based on Deep Reinforcement Learning," it was revealed that trust, perceived usefulness, and enjoyment play pivotal roles as positive predictors of customers' purchase intentions, particularly concerning the provision of honest offerings. Additionally, the study investigated customers' attitudes toward the sincerity of offerings provided by selected online delivery services.

Similarly, the research conducted by Belanger, Hiller, and Smith, titled "Trustworthiness in Electronic Commerce: The Role of Privacy, Security, and Site

Attributes," underscores the significance of efficient order dispatching and dynamic adjustment of delivery routes for the success of online-to-offline (O2O) businesses. The exponential growth in transactions facilitated by popular online food ordering platforms highlights the critical importance of addressing challenges associated with dispatching orders amidst computational complexities. Moreover, the study explored the impact of route recalibration through applications on delivery time within the context of selected online delivery services.

Table 3.3
Level of Customer Satisfaction with the E-Service Quality of Selected Online Deliveries in terms of Privacy

Privacy I felt the online delivery service...	DELIVERY APP A			DELIVERY APP B		
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Protected my shopping behavior information	3.84	Agree	5	4.10	Agree	4
Not shared my personal information	3.89	Agree	4	4.16	Agree	2.5
Protected my financial information	4.00	Agree	1	4.12	Agree	3
Is safe that the existing measures for payment security effectively safeguard against potential threats	3.93	Agree	3	4.24	Strongly Agree	1
Is trustworthy to the effectiveness	3.95	Agree	2	4.16	Agree	2.5

of the payment security system currently in place.

General Weighted Mean	3.92	Agree	4.15	Agree
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Table 3.3 presents the level of customer satisfaction with the e-service quality of selected online deliveries in terms of privacy. It can be noticed that the indicator that ranked first was the indicator that states, “I felt the online delivery service protected my financial information” with a mean of 4.21 for food delivery service A and “I felt the online delivery service is safe that the existing measures for payment security effectively safeguard against potential threats” with the mean of 4.24 for food delivery service B. It was followed by the indicator that states, “I felt the online delivery service is trustworthy to the effectiveness of the payment security system currently in place” with a mean of 3.95 for food delivery service A and both of “I felt the online delivery service not shared my personal information” as well as “I felt the online delivery service is trustworthy to the effectiveness of the payment security system currently in place” with the mean of 4.16 for food delivery service B. Next to it were the indicators that stated, “I felt the online delivery service is safe that the existing measures for payment security effectively safeguard against potential threats” with a mean of 3.93 for food delivery service A and “I felt the online delivery service protected my financial information” with a mean of 4.12 for food delivery service B. It was followed by the indicator that states, “I felt the online delivery service did not share my personal information” with a mean of 3.89 for food delivery service A. Lastly, both of the delivery app has the lowest for the indicator that stated, “I felt the online service protected my shopping behavior information” with the mean of 3.84 for food delivery service A and 4.10 for food delivery service B. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents.

In general, the respondents agreed with the respondents about the level of customer satisfaction with the e-service quality of selected online deliveries in terms of privacy with a general weighted mean of 3.92 for food delivery service A and 4.15 for food delivery service B.

According to the findings elucidated by Krishna, Krishnan, and Sebastian in their study titled "Understanding the Process of Building Institutional Trust Among Digital Payment Users Through National Cybersecurity Commitment Trustworthiness Cues: A Critical Realist Perspective," it was revealed that consumers base their decisions regarding the disclosure of private information on their perceptions of trustworthiness, regardless of whether the merchant operates solely in the electronic domain or has a physical presence as well.

Additionally, the study looked into how important it was for customers to purchase intentions for three kinds of web attributes: security, privacy, and pleasure characteristics (including convenience, simplicity of use, and visual appeal). Notably, when consumers think about their desire to make a purchase, privacy and security elements were determined to be less important than enjoyment features. A discussion of the ramifications of these findings and an explanation of the research agenda for the future round out the paper. However, concerning the trustworthiness of applications, consumers express apprehension regarding the safeguarding of their personal information.

Table 3.4
Level of Customer Satisfaction with the E-Service Quality of Selected Online Deliveries in terms of System

System I felt the online delivery service...	DELIVERY APP A			DELIVERY APP B		
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Was always available.	3.84	Agree	3	4.04	Agree	2
Did not crush or buffering.	3.89	Agree	2	3.91	Agree	3
Offer readily available customer support through multiple channels like phone, email, live chat, and social media	4.00	Agree	1	4.09	Agree	1
General Weighted Mean	3.91	Agree		4.01	Agree	

Table 3.4 presents the level of customer satisfaction with the e-service quality of selected online deliveries in terms of the system. It can be noticed that the indicator that ranked first was the indicator that states, "I felt the online delivery service Offer readily

available customer support through multiple channels like phone, email, live chat, and social media.” with a mean of 4.00 for food delivery service A and 4.09 for food delivery service B. It was followed by the indicator that states, “I felt the online delivery service Did not crush or buffering.” with a mean of 3.84 for food delivery service A and “I felt the online delivery service was always available” with a mean of 4.04 for food delivery service B. Lastly was the indicator that states, “I felt the online delivery service was always available” with the mean of 3.84 for food delivery service A and “I felt the online delivery service Did not crush or buffering.” with a mean of 3.91 for food delivery service B as the lowest indicator. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents.

In general, the people interviewed were of the same opinion concerning how satisfied customers are with the selected e-service quality of online deliveries in relation to the system. The average weighted mean was 3.91 for food delivery service A and 4.01 for food delivery service B.

As discovered by R et al. in 2018, to improve the food delivery service it is necessary to create a system that prevents major errors on the user’s side – changes in profiles by accident – and secures food items tracking using GPS. They should also provide feedback and recommendations for the service providers, to keep the customer database safe . In this case, the goal of improving the process is once again important to reduce the risk of customer dissatisfaction, something that could be similar to interactions between waiting staff and guests. Too much interaction without food service might lead to impatience.

According to Jeon and Jeong (2017) , employers should maintain a superior website and online application since it plays a vital role in retaining clients, promoting website revisits, and sustaining loyalty. Based on the review of literature, the past research has consistently measured the phenomenon of customers’ interactions with a company’s website or online application on their following behaviors. (Jeon and Jeong 2017; Pee et al., 2018)

Research Question 2: Assessment on the Level of Customer’s Satisfaction in Food Quality on Online Deliveries

**Table 3.5
Level of Customer Satisfaction with the Food Quality of Online Food Delivery**

Food Quality I felt the delivery service...	DELIVERY APP A			DELIVERY APP B		
	Weighted mean	Verbal interpretation	Rank	Weighte d mean	Verbal interpretation	Rank
Food was served hot and fresh.	3.76	Agree	8	4.19	Agree	3

Food is tasty and flavorful	4.02	Agree	2	4.36	Strongly Agree	1
Pleasing appearance of food	3.92	Agree	4.5	4.21	Strongly Agree	2.5
Ingredients are excellent in quality	3.94	Agree	3	4.16	Agree	4.5
Menu has a good variety of item	4.08	Agree	1	4.21	Strongly Agree	2.5
Food presentation is visually attractive.	3.92	Agree	4.5	4.16	Agree	4.5
The restaurants offers healthy options	3.87	Agree	6	4.07	Agree	5.5
The restaurants offers fresh food	3.89	Agree	5	4.07	Agree	5.5
Food is served at the appropriate temperature	3.74	Agree	9	3.99	Agree	6
The food was truly outstanding, exceeded all expectations in taste, freshness, presentation, and overall experience	3.82	Agree	7	4.21	Strongly Agree	2.5
neral Weighted Mean	3.89	Agree		4.16	Agree	

Table 3.5 presents the level of customer satisfaction with the food quality of online food delivery. It can be noticed that the indicator that ranked first was the indicator that states, "Menu has a good variety of items." with a mean of 4.08 for food delivery service

A, for food delivery service B the rank 1 was “food is tasty, and flavorful” with a mean of 4.36. It was followed by the indicator that states, “food is tasty and flavorful.” with a mean of 4.02 for food delivery service A, while for food delivery service B there were three statements that ranked second “Pleasing appearance of food”, “Menu has a good variety of items”, and “The food was truly outstanding, exceeded all expectations in taste, freshness, presentation, and overall experience” with a mean of 4.21. Then followed by rank three from food delivery service A with a mean of 3.94 “Ingredients are excellent in quality”, for food delivery service B with a total mean of 4.19 “Food was served hot and fresh”. Next to it were the indicators for food delivery service A which stated, “Pleasing appearance of food.” and “Food presentation is visually attractive” with a mean of 3.92, on the other hand for food delivery service B “Ingredients are excellent in quality” and “Food presentation is visually attractive” tied in fourth rank with a mean of 4.16.

It was followed by the indicators of food delivery service A that stated, “The restaurant offers fresh food” with a mean of 3.89, for the food delivery service B indicator “The restaurant offers the healthy option” and “The restaurant offers fresh food” with a mean of 4.07 as rank five. Next to it was the indicator for food delivery service A which stated, “The restaurant offers healthy options” with a mean of 3.87 and for food delivery service B “Food is served at the appropriate temperature” got the lowest rank for food delivery service B with a mean of 3.99. Then followed by the indicators of food delivery service A “Menu has a good variety of items”, “The food was truly outstanding, exceeded all expectations in taste, freshness, presentation, and overall experience” and “Food was served hot and fresh” with mean 3.82 and 3.76 respectively. Lastly, the indicator for food delivery service A states, “Food is served at the appropriate temperature.” with a mean of 3.74. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents.

Overall, the participants agreed on the level of customer satisfaction of the quality of food from online food delivery service A, providing a weighted mean of 3.89. Contrarily, the overall weighted mean for the quality of food from service B was 4.16.

According to Myo Min Aung and Yoon Seok Chang's study titled "Temperature Management for the Quality Assurance of a Perishable Food Supply Chain," (Aung & Chang, 2014) due to the inherent sensitivity of perishable foods to time and temperature, meticulous care is essential throughout their journey from harvesting to consumption. Temperature emerges as a critical determinant in extending the shelf life and preserving the quality of perishable goods. Refrigeration stands out as a widely adopted method to impede bacterial growth and prevent food spoilage. Effective control and management of temperature play a pivotal role in ensuring the delivery of perishables in optimal condition, thereby safeguarding consumer health and satisfaction. The study addresses strategies aimed at refining the process of defining optimal target temperatures for every food item delivered by selected online delivery services to customers' residences.

Research Question 3: Test of Difference between the Level of Customer Satisfaction on the E-service Quality on selected Online Deliveries and on Food Quality of Online Food Delivery

Table 3.6
Test of Difference between Level of Customer Satisfaction on the E-service Quality on selected Online Deliveries and on Food Quality of Online Food Delivery

	Mean	N	SD	Computed T-value	Critical T-value	Decision	Interpretation
E-service Quality	4.05	120	0.76	0.36	1.96	Accept null hypothesis	Not significant
Food Quality	4.09		0.77				

Table 3.6 presents the significant differences between the level of customer satisfaction on the e-service quality of selected online deliveries and on food quality of online food delivery. The table shows that the computed value of 0.36 is not significant at the 0.05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis should be accepted. It implies that there is no significant difference between the level of customer satisfaction with the e-service quality of selected online deliveries and the quality of online food delivery.

CONCLUSIONS

1. In relation of efficiency, Delivery Application A was apparent as all the items have a weighted mean of 3. On the other hand, food delivery service B's weighted mean was 4.27, higher than the former, demonstrating moderate approval. It is evident that in e-service and quality of the food, Delivery Application B is superior to Delivery Application A in the rate of customer satisfaction.
2. In respect to fulfillment, Delivery Application A has exhibited acceptable performance with regards to client contentment, averaging at 3.86. Conversely, Delivery Application B has garnered superior evaluations, boasting an average of 4.17. This suggests that although both applications function adequately in terms of satisfaction; Delivery Application B holds a slight advantage in satisfaction for customers.

3. Delivery App A has performed satisfactorily with respect to customer satisfaction in terms of fulfillment, with a mean of 3.86. Delivery App B on the other hand, fared better as shown by average rating of 4.17 as compared to the former delivery app. This means that although they are both good enough for fulfillment; however it is observed that Delivery App B appears to be slightly more satisfying for customers than its counterpart.
4. In regard to privacy, Delivery App A has performed satisfactorily in terms of user satisfaction with its privacy policies, with an average rating of 3.92. On the other hand, Delivery App B has received higher ratings, with an overall mean of 4.15, indicating a high level of satisfaction with its privacy features. This suggests that even while both apps offer adequate privacy protections, Delivery App B might have a slight advantage in terms of user acceptance.
5. Delivery App A has demonstrated satisfactory system performance across all metrics, and consumers are usually satisfied with the functionality of the system. The weighted average score of 3.91 overall suggests that users regard Delivery App A's system features to be satisfactory. Delivery App B, on the other hand, scored higher, with a weighted average of 4.01 overall, indicating a little higher degree of satisfaction with its system features. Both delivery apps offer acceptable system features, but Delivery App B appears to have a slight advantage in customer satisfaction. Further research is needed to identify areas for improvement and understand customer preferences.
6. In terms of Food Quality of Online Food Delivery, Delivery App A has performed adequately in all aspects of food quality and customers largely agree about its food quality. The overall weighted average of 3.89 means that Delivery App A's customers are satisfied with the quality of their food. Conversely, Delivery App B received higher ratings in many metrics, signifying a high degree of satisfaction with the food quality offered by it. While both platforms have good enough food, Delivery App B appears to be more pleasing to its users than Delivery App A. Therefore, this result is important for business owners when considering a delivery platform since customer experience and loyalty are influenced greatly by the quality of their foods.
7. In terms of significant differences between the level of customer satisfaction on the e-service quality of selected online deliveries and on food quality of online food delivery. The study found no significant difference in customer satisfaction between e-service quality and food quality in online food delivery services, indicating that the null hypothesis should be accepted. This suggests that customers do not perceive a significant difference in satisfaction levels between the two. However, it is important to note that the statistical test may not indicate a noticeable difference, as other factors like customer preferences and experiences could still impact satisfaction and perception of service quality.

Recommendations

With the outcomes and discussions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. In terms of efficiency, the businesses intending for ways to increase customer satisfaction and improve service quality should weigh the advantages and disadvantages of each app when choosing a platform. Both of the delivery applications A and B should focus on their well-organized applications for the easy browsing of the customers who will try their app.
2. Food Delivery app A should fulfill the need of delivering the food on time that is suitable to the time frame that was given in the application so that the customer will not be mad as the promised delivery time frame of the food. Food Delivery App B on the other hand suggests that keep the product in stock as it is the lowest indicator in results, researchers suggest that they should update their application on what was readily on the menu or what is the product that is out of stock so that the customers will not be surprised at the end.
3. For both Food Delivery App, A and Food Delivery App B, a paradigm shift makes almost everything done with technologies, with that it can be also a platform for people who take advantage of other people by using their resources and identity to get something important from them. That is why it is important to make the platform safe and free from harmful hackers, making the customers feel safe and at ease with the service to protect their shopping behavior information, because it's crucial to offer the product even in the absence of personal information, customers will feel more comfortable providing it if the security system is reliable.
4. The system that we use in every online food delivery application plays a crucial role as it is the center of communication for both customers and the restaurants. In Food Delivery App A, it says that the systems should always be available with that, food applications must be aware on how their applications should work in terms of the daily basis and look for loopholes that the customers might see in terms of the availability of their application so that they can do better to satisfy their customer. Food Delivery App B, when it comes to mobile meal delivery apps, platform usability has a big impact on consumer happiness. In addition to ensuring seamless purchasing, browsing, and payment procedures, a well-designed system reduces annoyance and increases customer engagement. Mobile food delivery apps may improve customer satisfaction, streamline restaurant operations, and open the door for long-term success in the market by making smart investments in these areas.
5. Both Food Delivery App A and Food Delivery App B should focus on the proper temperature of the food. Foods must be carefully handled throughout the entire chain, as they can be temperature- and time-sensitive by nature. The most crucial element in extending or preserving the shelf life of perishables is temperature. They can innovate packaging that maintains its temperature for a longer time, to ensure the quality and temperature of the food being delivered.
6. In table 3.6, it says that there is no significant difference between the level of customer satisfaction on the e-service quality on selected online deliveries and on food quality of online food delivery. The efficiency, fulfillment, privacy, and

systems go well as they use the application for the better transaction while using their preferred online applications, with these factors they can also ensure that the quality of the food that the consumer entrusted to them meets their expectation. It is also recommended that they should continue the quality service the applications already have or must exceed the current one as they provide more excellence about the application.

7. The researchers recommend expanding the sample in a subsequent study through ongoing guest interviews or surveys conducted over a long period to learn more about food delivery applications. By the fact that the respondents of this study are frequent users of the food delivery applications, it is suggested that the future researcher can include first-timers or the ones that are new in terms of using the app for a better understanding and analysis of the usage of the application.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The participants in this study were treated with confidentiality, anonymity, and informed consent while adhering to ethical standards. Before collecting data, the study received ethical approval from the appropriate research ethics committee. The study was held accountable for any issues and ethical standards that might emerge. The study's instruments were evaluated and approved by the researcher's advisor. Regarding the problem statement, the researchers will offer survey questions. By accepting the researcher's consent form and indicating that they fully understood the survey's requirements and that they accepted to participate in filling out the questionnaires that were provided to them, the participants were able to demonstrate their cooperation. The consent form outlines the study's goals and rationale for conducting the survey, as well as the participants' promise to keep their data confidential. Additionally, the responders' information was kept private and discreet along with the data protection policies

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REFERENCES

- AlBalushi, T. H. (2021, March 26). E-services quality: A perspective of service providers and service users. IntechOpen. <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/75955>
- Annaraud, K., & Berezina, K. (2020, May 25). Predicting satisfaction and intentions to use online food delivery: What really makes a difference? *Journal of Foodservice Business Research*, 23(4), 305–323. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15378020.2020.1768039>
- Aung, M. M., & Chang, Y. S. (2014). Temperature management for the quality assurance of a perishable food supply chain. *Food Control*, 40, 198–207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2013.11.016>
- Banerjee, Dr. S. P., Jain, Dr. D., & Nayyar, Dr. R. (2019). Measuring service quality of food delivery services: A study of ... Measuring Service Quality of Food Delivery Services: A study of Generation Z. https://www.ajhtl.com/uploads/7/1/6/3/7163688/article_41__vol_8_2__2019_in_dia.pdf
- Chandrasekhar, N., Gupta, S., & Nanda, N. (2019, June 12). *Food Delivery Services and Customer Preference: A Comparative Analysis*. *Journal of Foodservice Business Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15378020.2019.1626208>
- Chaudhari, A. (2021, September 29). *What is Descriptive Research Design?* Voxco. <https://www.voxco.com/blog/descriptive-research-design/>
- Cheng, C., Chang, Y., & Chen, C. (2021). Construction of a service quality scale for the online food delivery industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 95, 102938. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2021.102938>
- Elsharnouby, T. H., and Mahrous, A. A. (2015). Customer participation in online co-creation experience: The role of e-service quality. *J. Res. Interact. Marke.* 9, 313–336. doi: 10.1108/JRIM-06-2014-0038
- Fan, W., Shao, B., & Dong, X. (2022). Effect of e-service quality on customer engagement behavior in community e-commerce. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.965998>
- Goraya, M. A. S., Jing, Z., Shareef, M. A., Imran, M., Malik, A., and Akram, M. S. (2021). An investigation of the drivers of social commerce and e-word-of-mouth intentions: Elucidating the role of social commerce in E-business. *Electron. Mark.* 31, 181–195. doi: 10.1007/s12525-019-00347-w
- Hung, S. Y., Chen, C., and Huang, N. H. (2014). An integrative approach to understanding customer satisfaction with e-service of online stores. *J. Electron. Commer. Res.* 15, 40–57.

- Jeon, M. M., & Jeong, M. (2017). Customers' perceived website service quality and its effects on e-loyalty. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(1), 438-457. doi:10.1108/IJCHM-02-2015-0054
- Kim, W. G., Ng, C. Y. N., & Kim, Y. (2009, March 1). *Influence of institutional DINESERV on customer satisfaction, return intention, and word-of-mouth*. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2008.03.005>
- Krishna, B., Krishnan, S., & Sebastian, M. P. (2023). Understanding the process of building institutional trust among digital payment users through national cybersecurity commitment trustworthiness cues: a critical realist perspective. *Information Technology & People*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/itp-05-2023-0434>
- Leo, G., Hurriyati, R., & Hendrayati, H. (2022). Online Food Delivery Service: The Role of e-service quality and food quality on customer loyalty. *Advances in Economics, Business, and Management Research*.
<https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.220701.049>
- Lopez De Leon , S., Acuña, M. J., Bacolod, R., Dela Cruz, A., Navarro, N., Roldan, J., Salumbre, A., Sangines, R. E., & Zaguirre, P. S. (2017). *CUSTOMER SERVICE AND CUSTOMERS' SATISFACTION IN JOLLIBEE*. Studocu.
<https://www.studocu.com/ph/document/university-of-perpetual-help-system-jonelta/enterprise-research-2/original-full-copy-of-thesis/12852742>
- Luo, N., Wang, Y., Zhang, M., Niu, T., and Tu, J. (2020). Integrating community and e-commerce to build a trusted online second-hand platform: Based on the perspective of social capital. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change* 153:119913. doi: 10.1016/j.techfore.2020.119913
- Nikolopoulou, K. (2023, June 22). What Is Purposive Sampling? | Definition & Examples. Scribbr.
<https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/purposive-sampling/>
- Pee, L., Jiang, J., & Klein, G. (2018). E-store loyalty: Longitudinal comparison of website usefulness and satisfaction. *International Journal of Market Research*, January, 12, 1-17. doi: 10.1177/1470785317752045
- Rozekhi, N. A., Hussin, S., Siddiqe, A. S. K. a. R., Ab, P. D., Rashid, & Salmi, N. S. (2016). The influence of food quality on customer satisfaction in fine dining restaurant : Case in Penang. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-Influence-of-Food-Quality-on-Customer-in-Fine-%3A-Rozekhi-Hussin/3ddddd2c7cef1107baf6ce34d56a9620cd82daf83>
- Sharma, G. and Lijuan, W. (2015), "The effects of online service quality of e-commerce Websites on user satisfaction", *The Electronic Library*, Vol. 33 No. 3, pp. 468-485. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EL-10-2013-0193>
- Siedlecki, S. L. (2020, January 1). Understanding Descriptive Research Designs and Methods. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*; Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/nur.0000000000000493>
- Studocu. (n.d.). Survey Questionnaire - SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE To the Respondent, We are currently conducting our – Studocu.
<https://www.studocu.com/ph/document/university-of-perpetual-help-system-jonelta/survey-of-literature-philworld/survey-questionnaire/12852779>

- Suhartanto, D., Dean, D. L., Leo, G., & Triyuni, N. N. (2019, January). Millennial Experience with Online Food Home Delivery: A Lesson from Indonesia. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344703604_Millennial_Experience_with_Online_Food_Home_Delivery_A_Lesson_from_Indonesia/fulltext/5f8a3faa92851c14bccc5b47/Millennial-Experience-with-Online-Food-Home-DeliveryA-Lesson-from-Indonesia.pdf
- Wang, J., Cai, S., Xie, Q., and Chen, L. (2021). The influence of community engagement on seller opportunistic behaviors in e-commerce platform. *Electron. Commer. Res.* 1, 1–29. doi: 10.1007/s10660-021-09469-w
- Wu, J., Hwang, J. N., Sharkhuu, O., & Tsogt-Ochir, B. (2018, March 1). Shopping online and off-line? Complementary service quality and image congruence. *Yà-tài Guǎnlǐ Pínglùn/Asia Pacific Management Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2017.01.004>
- Zou, G., Tang, J., Yilmaz, L., & Kong, X. (2021). Online food ordering delivery strategies based on deep reinforcement learning. *Applied Intelligence*, 52(6), 6853–6865. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10489-021-02750-3>